

A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION BETWEEN AMAZON AND FLIPKART WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TOWARDS COIMBATORE DISTRICT

KL. Chandramohan* & M. Vadivel**

* Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Sri Ramakrishna Mission
Vidyalaya College of Arts and Science (Autonomous), Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

** Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Sri Ramakrishna Mission Vidyalaya College of Arts and
Science (Autonomous), Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

Amazon and Flipkart are one of the leading online shopping websites in India. In this paper, an attempt has been made to find customers satisfaction towards amazon and flipkart. A sample of 100 respondent's were conveniently selected from Coimbatore District. The findings were analyzed using simple percentage analysis, chi-square test and Friedman's ranking test. Findings reveal that female customers whose annual income is high are highly satisfied towards amazon and flipkart. The research also concludes that even though amazon is giving branded and quality product but customer are very much attracted towards the best services of flipkart.

Key Words: Amazon, Flipkart, Online Shopping & Customer Satisfaction

Introduction:

Online shopping business transactions are conducted directly between a company and customers who are the end-users of its products or services. While most companies that sell their products/ services directly to customers. Online retailers, as well as other companies that sold products and services to customers directly through the internet without any middleman. Online shopping was first introduced in the 1960s via an electronic data interchange (EDI) on value-added networks (VANs). The medium grew with the increased availability of internet access and the advent of popular online sellers in the 1990s and early 2000s. Amazon was one of the first to began operating as a book-shipping business in Jeff Bezos' garage in 1995. After the arrival of amazon, flipkart, snapdeal, ebay many leading online shopping websites have been introduced in the market.

Amazon:

It is an American electronic commerce and cloud computing company based in Seattle, Washington that was founded by Jeff Bezos on July 5, 1994. It has separate retail websites for the United States, the United Kingdom and Ireland, France, Canada, Germany, Italy, Spain, Netherlands, Australia, Brazil, Japan, China, India, and Mexico. amazon.com's product lines available at its website include books, DVDs, music CDs, videotapes and software, apparel, baby products, customer electronics, beauty products, gourmet food, groceries, health and personal-care items, industrial & scientific supplies, kitchen items, jewelry, watches, lawn and garden items, musical instruments, sporting goods, tools, automotive items and toys & games. It is one of the leading and reputed online e-commerce platforms acknowledged at a wide scale all over the country.

Flipkart:

It is an electronic commerce company was founded in October 2007 by Sachin Bansal and Binny Bansal and headquartered in Bengaluru, India. It is a reputed and one of the esteemed e-commerce platforms used simply to access all over the world. flipkart.com's product line are available at its websites include all electronics, appliances, anything related to men and women, baby and kids wear, home and furniture, books and more, it is the best platform to seek for.

Review of Literature:

Prof. Ashish Bhatt (2014) examined that online shopping is gaining popularity among people specially the younger generation but in today scenario to become equally popular among all age groups e-marketing will have to cover a longer distance. The main objective of this research paper is to find Customer Attitude towards Online Shopping in Selected Regions of Gujarat. Many people from different age groups are doing online shopping regularly. This research concludes that attitude of customers is changing with the time and customers are finding online shopping very comfortable because of many reasons.

Prashant Singh (2014) examined that the main objective of the research is to find the customer's buying behaviour towards online shopping. The research stated that future of e-retailers in India looking very bright. Nowadays e-retailers give customers the best way to save money and time through purchasing online within the range of budget. One of the leading e-retailer flipkart also offering some of the best prices and completely hassle-free shopping experience. The research concludes that whole concept of online shopping has altered in India in terms of customer's purchasing or buying behavior.

Amit Saha (2015) revealed impact of the increasing trend of online shopping over the various fixed shop retailers. This research study examined the various aspects about how retail businesses are being affected and also the various recovery mechanisms they are coming up with to counter those e-stores in their race of

survival. This research study also found the effect upon the profitability of the various concerns due to increasing trend for online shopping.

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the demographic profile of the online shopping customer in Coimbatore District.
- ✓ To compare the customer satisfaction towards Amazon and Flipkart.

Limitations of the Study:

- ✓ The study is restricted to the selected sample of Amazon and Flipkart customer in Coimbatore District and hence the result of the study cannot be generalized.
- ✓ The statistical methods used to analyze the data have their own limitation.
- ✓ All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.

Research Methodology:

Amazon and Flipkart customers in Coimbatore District are taken for the study. A total sample of 100 respondents consists of each 50 customers of Amazon and Flipkart. These respondents were conveniently selected from Coimbatore District. Primary data is collected through well structured questionnaire. Secondary data needed for the study was collected from magazines, journals, books, websites etc., For the purpose of analysis the data were further processed by using statistical tools. The statistical tools are

- ✓ Simple Percentage
- ✓ Chi-Square Test
- ✓ Friedman Ranking Test

Analysis and Interpretation:

Demographic Profile of the Respondents:

Table 1 describes the demographic profile of the online shopping customer. Out of 100 respondents who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most (62%) of the respondents are female, (46%) of the respondents age is up to 25 years, most (48%) of the respondents are graduates, maximum number (39%) of respondents are employees, the annual income of (56%) respondents is Rs.1,00,000 to Rs.2,50,000, (61%) belongs to nuclear family, 58% of the respondents number of members in family are between 2 to 5, (43%) respondents purchase are influenced through Friends/Relatives and (35%) of the respondents purchase clothes/accessories through online.

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Factors	Number of Respondents N=100	Percentage
Gender		
Male	38	38
Female	62	62
Age (Years)		
Up to 25	46	46
26 to 45	29	29
Above 45	25	25
Educational Qualification		
Up to School Level	12	12
Graduate	48	48
Post Graduate	40	40
Occupation		
Professional	21	21
Employee	39	39
Business	26	26
Others	14	14
Annual Income		
Up to Rs.1,00,000	22	22
Rs.1,00,001 to Rs.2,50,000	56	56
Above Rs.2,50,000	22	22
Type of Family		
Joint	39	39
Nuclear	61	61
Number of Members		
Upto2	20	20
2 to 5	58	58
Above 5	22	22
Influence to Purchase		
Family	30	30

Advertisement	27	27
Friends/Relatives	43	43
Products purchased through online		
Clothes/ Accessories	35	35
All type of Tickets	26	26
Electronic Goods	24	24
Books/Medicines	15	15

Table 2: Relationship between Customer Demographic Profile and Level of Satisfaction towards Amazon and Flipkart

Variables	Level of Challenge			Total	χ^2 Value	Table Value	Remarks
	Low	Moderate	High				
Gender							
Male	12	18	8	38	7.634	5.991	S
Female	16	33	13	62			
Age (Years)							
Up to 25	16	20	10	46	12.499	9.488	S
26 to 50	6	14	9	29			
Above 50	7	10	8	25			
Educational Qualification							
Up to School Level	2	6	4	12	6.178	9.488	NS
Graduate	18	18	12	48			
Post Graduate	14	16	10	40			
Annual Income							
Up to Rs.1,00,000	8	7	7	22	14.823	9.488	S
Rs.1,00,001 to Rs.2,50,000	19	21	16	56			
Above Rs.2,50,000	4	8	10	22			
Type of Family							
Nuclear Family	7	23	9	39	3.598	5.991	NS
Joint Family	18	31	12	61			
Occupation							
Professional	5	10	6	21	16.789	12.458	S
Employee	14	15	10	39			
Business	9	11	6	26			
Others	4	6	4	14			

*significant at 5% percent level

Table no.2 depicts the relationship between customers selected demographic variables and Level of satisfaction towards amazon and flipkart. It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is greater than the table value at five percent level, there exists any significant association between gender, age, annual income, occupation of the customers and level of satisfaction towards amazon and flipkart. Thus the hypothesis is rejected.

It is clear that, the calculated Chi-square value is lesser than the table value at five percent level, there exists no significant association between educational qualifications, type of family of the customers and level of satisfaction towards amazon and flipkart. Hence the hypothesis is accepted.

Table 3: Customers Satisfaction – Friedman Rank Test

Factors	Amazon		Flipkart	
	Average Rank	Rank	Average Rank	Rank
Low Price	3.4	3	3.2	3
Service	2.5	4	4.8	1
Suitability	1.8	5	2.4	4
Variety of Choice	3.9	2	1.3	5
Quality	4.6	1	3.9	2

The above table shows about the Friedman Rank Test for customers satisfaction shows that there is a relationship between the ranks given. The satisfaction factor of the customers towards the online shopping through Friedman rank test, it is found that majority of the amazon customers are satisfied with the quality, variety of choice, low price, service and suitability. It is also found that majority of the flipkart customers are satisfied with the service, quality, low price, suitability and variety of choice. Thus, it found from the above table that most of the amazon customers are satisfied with the quality of the product and most of the flipkart customers are satisfied with the service for their product.

Conclusion:

Online shopping in India is growing between 2010 to till. Internet penetration is increasing in India due to the increasing base of tele communicating networking sites, social networks and sale of mobiles in India. Online shopping is one of the most attractive, widely accepted, highly appreciated shopping trend in present world. Amazon and flipkart are the two top leading online shopping websites. People also very much preferred and satisfied towards them. Although the customers are satisfied with online shopping they also face some problems due to many technological and false advertisement. This problem can be overcome by educating the customers. The research concludes that eventhough amazon is giving branded and quality products but customers are very much attracted towards the best services of flipkart.

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